

District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC): Intervention for Teachers' Apprehension to Teach Practical Research: An Action Research

DOI:

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effect of the District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC) as an intervention to address teachers' apprehensions about teaching practical research. Employing a qualitative group case design, the research aims to evaluate the effect of DsLAC on teachers' readiness to teach practical research subjects. The central problem addressed is how the implementation of DsLAC contributes to reducing teachers' apprehensions regarding practical research instruction. The results reveal a significant improvement in teachers' confidence and competence in delivering practical research content after participating in the DsLAC program. The discussion highlights the positive influence of collaborative learning and professional development opportunities provided by DsLAC on enhancing teachers' pedagogical skills. The findings underscore the value of targeted interventions like DsLAC in improving teacher preparedness and instructional quality in practical research education. The study concludes that DsLAC effectively mitigates teachers' apprehensions and recommends further integration of similar interventions to support educators in effectively teaching practical research subjects

Keywords: *Descriptive research design, district action Cell (DsLAC), practical research, San Fernando 2, action Research.*

Context and Rationale

Every educational institution shares the common objective of pursuing the highest caliber of teachers, as they firmly believe that the quality of instruction significantly impacts the overall quality of learning. The Department of Education strongly emphasizes the importance of professional development interventions and recognizes the critical role of teacher capacity building. However, the noble goal of education faces a major obstacle in some schools because some teachers lack confidence and are apprehensive about teaching, especially when it comes to practical research subjects. Embracing the District Learning Action Cell approach, the San Fernando II District Research Coordinator come up with an innovative resolution for this issue. Through the implementation of this approach, teachers in San Fernando District II will receive the necessary assistance and resources to proficiently teach practical research subjects.

In line with this, Valdehueza et al. (2020) emphasize the crucial role of effective teachers in enhancing the education system and increasing learning standard. It was suggested that Education Supervisors consistently provide the Learning Action Cell (LAC) as top priority and take into account the suggested activities to further integrate 21st century capabilities. By putting the Learning Action Cell instructional designs into practice, teachers may optimize the advantages of cooperation among educators. According to DepEd Order No. 35, s. 2016, a Learning Action Cell was defined as a group of educators working together during learning sessions under the direction of the school principal or a designated LAC Leader to solve shared concerns.

One significant issue at San Fernando District II is that some teachers expressed their fear and hesitation about teaching practical research during the focus group discussion. Their lack of knowledge and practical experience in the field of research writing is the cause of their reluctance. This emphasizes how urgent it is to take extensive steps to empower these teachers and provide them with the skills and confidence they need to teach practical research. Mentoring and coaching support for teachers are imperative in addressing this issue. In short, teachers were facing the challenges such as the difficulty in giving instructions and producing an output.

To address the identified issue, the researchers propose the implementation of the District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC) as an intervention. The intervention involves collaborative learning sessions where teachers can share their challenges, exchange ideas, and receive guidance on teaching practical research. By providing a supportive and collaborative environment, the intervention approach aims to build teachers' confidence and capabilities in teaching practical research subjects.

The primary objective of this study is to evaluate how the District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC) intervention can effectively address teachers' apprehension to teach practical research. The ultimate aim is to overcome any resistance or hesitations that teachers may have towards teaching this subject by providing them with the necessary knowledge and support. Through the implementation of this innovative approach, teachers in San Fernando District II will have the chance to gain valuable insights and develop their interest in teaching practices for practical research.

Action Research Question

How does the DsLAC intervention impact teachers' confidence and instructional effectiveness in practical research?

Proposed Innovation, Intervention, or Strategy

In the San Fernando II District, there is a significant issue of teachers lacking confidence in teaching the Practical Research subject. This challenge poses a barrier to providing high-quality education to students. To address this concern, the research district coordinator plans to implement the District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC) as an intervention specifically designed to alleviate teachers' apprehensions in the San Fernando II District.

Pre-Implementation Phase. During the study, several careful steps are taken. Initially, the researcher secure permission from the principal of where the researcher is affiliated, and the district supervisor. Once approval is granted, the researchers organize focus group discussions with senior high school teachers from the San Fernando II District to listen to their worries and apprehensions about teaching practical research to students. The conversation during a focus group discussion center on the teachers' reluctance to teach the subject. Following the focus group, the researcher undertakes the required preparations to implement the intervention strategy, addressing the issues and concerns collected.

Implementation Phase. As part of the devised strategy, the researcher initiate the implementation of the District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC) to address the concerns of teachers in San Fernando II District when tasked with teaching the Practical Research subject. The DsLAC intervention encompasses collaborative learning sessions designed to alleviate apprehensions and enhance teaching practices. These sessions actively engage teachers in cooperative learning activities where they receive guidance on effective Practical Research instruction, exchange ideas, and discuss challenges they face. The primary objective is to cultivate a supportive environment that fosters knowledge-sharing, provides guidance, and collectively boosts confidence in delivering successful Practical Research lessons through mentoring and coaching.

In addition to facilitating collaborative learning sessions, the researchers ensure that research participants are well-informed about the study's objectives, parameters, and timeline. Prior to their involvement, participants are approached to secure their voluntary and informed consent, addressing any ethical considerations that may arise. This transparent approach underscores the researchers' commitment to upholding ethical standards and prioritizing the well-being and rights of the participants involved in the study.

The implementation of the strategy will be meticulously documented to capture the process, outcomes, and impact of the DsLAC intervention on teachers' confidence and instructional practices. By documenting each step of the intervention, researchers can evaluate the effectiveness of the strategy, identify areas for improvement, and gather valuable insights that can inform future interventions or adaptations. This documentation serves as a valuable tool for assessing the success of the initiative, highlighting best practices, and sharing lessons learned with stakeholders to drive continuous improvement and innovation in supporting educators in their professional development journey.

Post Implementation Phase. Following the intensive focus groups and collaborative training sessions, teachers have undergone a transformative journey, emerging with newfound confidence and enhanced skills to effectively teach the Practical Research course. Through the immersive activities facilitated by the District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC), the initial apprehensions that once plagued teachers have been alleviated, paving the way for a resurgence of self-assurance in their ability to deliver exceptional practical research instruction within the San Fernando II District. These experiences have not only bolstered their confidence but have also equipped them with the requisite knowledge and competencies essential for navigating the complexities of teaching Practical Research.

The collective wisdom and shared experiences garnered through the DsLAC activities have empowered teachers to create a more dynamic and interactive learning environment. This collaborative approach has enabled

them to refine their teaching methods, explore innovative strategies, and adapt to the ever-evolving landscape of education. As a result, the professional development attained through these initiatives extends beyond individual growth, positively impacting the overall quality of practical research education throughout the district. Teachers are no longer plagued by hesitation or uncertainty when faced with the task of teaching this subject, demonstrating a newfound readiness and enthusiasm to engage their students in meaningful and effective learning experiences.

Moreover, post-implementation of the intervention, the researchers meticulously compile the outcomes of the initiatives, analyze and discuss the findings, and progress towards finalizing the report. This involves a comprehensive review of the entire body of work, subjecting it to rigorous critique and evaluation to ensure accuracy and validity. Subsequently, the research report is submitted to the research committee for the final presentation, marking the culmination of the investigative process. The dissemination and utilization of the research findings are prioritized, with the researchers presenting the outcomes and sharing actionable recommendations for practical application and further research endeavors. By disseminating these insights and recommendations, the impact of the research extends beyond the confines of the study, contributing to the broader body of knowledge and informing future educational practices and initiatives.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Learning Action Cell and the Teachers

The Department of Education supports the professional development of the teachers through the learning action cell (Department Order 35, 2016). Teacher learning through LAC is a continuous process that promotes teachers' teaching skills, master new knowledge, develop new proficiency, which in turn, help improve students' learning (Verbo, 2020). Johnson et al. (2018), teacher shortages and other educational issues may be effectively addressed through collaborative learning methodologies. In schools with comparable resource limitations to those in the current study, the researchers investigated the effects of collaborative learning settings. They came to the conclusion that collaborative learning not only promotes peer support among students but also enhances learning outcomes, therefore reducing the negative impacts of teacher shortages on student education. According to Burton (2015), teacher collaboration has been shown to enhance instructional practices and student achievement. Furthermore, according to Darling-Hammond (2003), investing in the quality of teachers has a favorable impact on student learning outcomes, teacher effectiveness, and overall educational quality. It was also emphasized the significance of developing a high-quality teaching workforce. The report recommends giving hiring and retaining qualified teachers first priority in order to foster an atmosphere that supports academic advancement. This demonstrates the necessity of competitive pay, encouraging work environments, and ongoing professional development for drawing and retaining exceptional educators.

Guarino et al. (2006) identified the workable solutions to lessen the effect of teacher shortages on student performance. They emphasize how important focused interventions are in attracting and keeping qualified instructors, such as mentorship programs and incentives. Using seasoned mentors to assist new teachers can support their professional growth and classroom efficacy. Furthermore, offering incentives to teachers—like financial compensation or chances for career progression—encourages them to remain in the field, which eventually improves student achievement. Hughes (2012) posited that teachers with a great deal of experience have better teaching skills, which raises student achievement. Experienced educators are better positioned to support their students' increasing academic performance because of their abundance of information and abilities acquired over time. Furthermore, their competence makes the classroom a more productive and engaging place to study.

Student Learning

According to the research conducted by Khurshid and Ansari (2014), students' active learning is enhanced by observation and hands-on activities. When learners receive applied knowledge and skills through integrated practical implementation, their learning process accelerates. This approach also entails instances of trial and error during self-exploration. Barkley et al. (2014) said that students who participate in collaborative learning should gain significant knowledge and comprehension of the course material. In order to ensure that the vibrant small-group interactions result in educational outcomes rather than being just engaging on the surface without accomplishing instructional goals, the group activity that has been set should be in line with the learning objectives. Li (2021) focuses on the relationship between teacher apprehension and student classroom engagement. It says that the connection between communication apprehension experienced by EFL teachers and its impact on student engagement in classroom activities shall be addressed by examining the antecedents of teacher apprehension and discusses the importance of addressing this issue to enhance student learning.

Finally, the objective of this undertaking is to lighten-up the teachers from their challenges. This can be possible with the production of Intervention to Teachers' Apprehension to Teach Practical Research in the district where the teacher-respondents are stationed.

Action Research Methods

This section thoroughly discussed the research methodology, describing the research design, the target participants, data gathering, data analysis and ethical considerations.

Design

This study employs a qualitative group case research design to explore the experiences and the challenges of the teachers during the implementation and effectiveness of the District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC) intervention in improving the teaching of practical research in schools, specifically in District 2 of San Fernando. Following Thomas' (2006) suggestion, a general inductive approach will be used to analyze the qualitative data. This technique entails systematically classifying and categorizing the data to uncover patterns and themes.

By employing this approach, the research intends to offer a thorough explanation of the DsLAC intervention's implementation process and results, aiding in the creation of focused group discussion strategies and support networks that will raise the standard of education in different schools in the San Fernando district. Additionally, the research aims to evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention on teachers' apprehensions about teaching practical research and enhance their knowledge and capabilities in this area. The findings will provide valuable insights into effective strategies for improving practical research instruction and benefit teachers in District 2 of San Fernando by equipping them with the necessary knowledge and support.

Research Participants

District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC) is an intervention to address teachers' apprehension in teaching practical research. By complete enumeration, the participants of the study included the 35 selected senior high school teachers from San Fernando II District. Led by researcher, the San Fernando II District Research Coordinator, and committed teacher, this initiative will foster collaborative learning sessions where teachers can openly discuss their challenges, exchange creative ideas, and seek guidance on effectively instructing practical research. By involving these dedicated educators from various schools in the district, the intervention aims to provide comprehensive support and guidance in the teaching of practical research subjects.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering methods of this study will follow the following phases such as pre-data collection, actual data collection and post data collection.

Pre-data Collection. The initial phase of the study involves securing all necessary permissions to conduct the research. The researchers will first seek clearance from the Research Committee. Following this, a letter will be composed and sent to the School Principal's office, requesting permission to conduct the study and obtaining permission from the District Supervisor. Subsequently, letters will be addressed to all the administrator from San Fernando II District Senior High School informing them about the research.

Actual Data Collection. The intervention, spearheaded by the Research Coordinator of San Fernando District II, focuses on addressing the prevalent issue of fear and hesitation among teachers at San Fernando District Senior High School.

The teachers voiced their apprehensions about teaching practical research due to their limited understanding and experience. In order to address this, the researchers introduced the District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC) initiative, which facilitated collaborative learning sessions where teachers could openly discuss their concerns, share ideas, and receive guidance. The researcher then conducted a comprehensive evaluation of the participants' development in teaching the intricate subject of practical research by administering a detailed questionnaire. The main objective of this questionnaire is to evaluate how much teachers have improved their confidence in teaching practical research content to their students.

Post Data Collection. Following the implementation of the District Learning Action Cell and subsequent administration of the comprehensive questionnaire, the researcher gathers the data obtained from the survey. Subsequently, employing coding analysis, the researcher interpret the gathered information. The process of data interpretation serves as the foundation for the qualitative approach utilized in presenting the findings. Through

narrative descriptions, the researcher creates a compelling narrative that explains their apprehensions about teaching practical research subjects to the participants.

Data Analysis

To gain a more profound insight into the individual apprehensions and perspectives that have influenced the research outcomes, the study will leverage coding analysis. By applying the qualitative analysis method of coding, following the guidelines set by the University of Illinois, researchers can extract pertinent information from the data by delineating crucial details. This qualitative approach entails categorizing and interpreting teachers' responses to unveil their concerns and challenges in delivering practical research lessons.

This meticulous examination employs qualitative methods to pinpoint the specific apprehensions that teachers encounter when teaching practical research to students. The primary objective is to achieve a comprehensive understanding of teachers' overall effectiveness and extract valuable insights from their unique experiences contributing to this goal. This enhanced comprehension is essential for optimizing teaching outcomes for teachers and providing guidance for future enhancements in practical research education.

Through group case analysis, the study aims to delve into the nuances of teachers' apprehensions and viewpoints, shedding light on the intricacies that shape their teaching experiences. Using the step of qualitative descriptive analysis of Krippendorff, the process involves , (a) Transcription – converted the recorded interviews into written text accurately, that is reflecting the participants' words verbatim. . Ensure that the transcripts are accurate and reflect the participants' words verbatim. (b) Familiarization - read through the transcripts, familiarized with the content by reading through the interview transcripts a number of times with initial notes of the recurring ideas. (c) Coding – develop codes by identifying significant words, phrases, or sentences within the interview transcripts that are relevant to your research question. (d) Inductive or deductive coding – defined the codes and allowed the codes to emerge from the data itself. (e). Categorization- grouped and organized codes into categories and into broader categories or themes which involves identifying patterns and connections between the codes. (f) Data Reduction – summarized the data into a condensed and meaningful category retaining its core message. (g) Describe the findings: Wrote up a descriptive summary of each category or theme, using direct quotes from the interviews to support your findings. (h) Validation - reviewed and refined the themes accurately or that reflects the content of the interviews. (i) Outcome – based on the result, detailed description of the themes or categories that emerged from the interview data (Krippendorff, 2018). . By systematically analyzing and categorizing teachers' responses, researchers can uncover patterns, themes, and underlying factors influencing their apprehensions. This method allows for a detailed exploration of teachers' concerns, enabling a nuanced understanding of the challenges they face in teaching practical research.

Furthermore, the qualitative analysis will not only identify teachers' apprehensions but also offer insights into potential solutions and strategies for improvement. By understanding the specific concerns and viewpoints of teachers, the study can propose targeted interventions and professional development opportunities to address these challenges effectively. This tailored approach can lead to enhanced teacher confidence, improved instructional practices, and ultimately, better learning outcomes for students in practical research.

Ethical Consideration

In this research study, the participants' safety and well-being are of utmost importance. When performing the study, the researcher closely followed the established protocols outlined by ethical standards and principles in order to protect the study's safety and ethical integrity.

FINDINGS

This section delves into the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data related to educators' deficiencies in expertise and knowledge, especially when it comes to teaching subjects like Practical Research. The crucial role of education is significantly hindered in schools due to the inadequacies and lack of understanding among teachers, particularly in areas like Practical Research. Through a detailed examination of the collected data, the study sheds light on the challenges faced by educators and the impact of their limited knowledge on the quality of education provided.

Furthermore, the analysis delves into the root causes of the educators' apprehension and lack of confidence in delivering Practical Research lessons. It explores the factors contributing to their reluctance and uncertainties, highlighting the need for targeted interventions and professional development opportunities to address these issues effectively. By identifying and addressing these challenges, the education system can work towards enhancing the quality of instruction and ultimately improving student learning outcomes in subjects like Practical Research. Through the DsLAC, technical assistance was provided. Follow-ups were made through the

group chat to keep the teachers reminded and keep them monitored. Further, any updates can be channeled through the group chat while then they meet certain difficulties, for instance, the craft of the title of the research paper, technical assistance can be provided while other teachers can share their ideas freely.

Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Table 1
Teachers' Experiences Before the District Learning Action Cell

Before the Intervention (District Learning Action Cell)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teachers expressed apprehension in teaching Practical Research • Teachers felt afraid and lacked confidence in teaching Practical Research • Teachers had limited knowledge in teaching Practical Research • Teachers were hesitant to teach Practical Research • Teachers worried about the challenges of teaching Practical Research
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Before the intervention of the District Learning Action Cell, educators were grappling with significant apprehension and a noticeable lack of confidence when it came to teaching Practical Research. Their unease stemmed from feeling ill-equipped and uncertain about the intricacies of this subject area. This lack of confidence led to initial hesitancy among teachers to embrace the responsibility of teaching Practical Research, as they felt unprepared to navigate its complexities effectively.

Moreover, teachers pointed out the inherent challenges in transmitting Practical Research knowledge to their students. They recognized the multifaceted nature of the subject matter, acknowledging the necessity for further study and evaluation to enhance their instructional practices. This acknowledgment underscores their commitment to professional growth and development, indicating a willingness to bolster their competencies in Practical Research for the benefit of their students.

The initial reservations and apprehensions expressed by educators are not uncommon when faced with unfamiliar or demanding subject matter. The introduction of the District Learning Action Cell holds promise in providing the necessary support and resources to help educators address their concerns and cultivate confidence in delivering impactful Practical Research lessons. By offering targeted assistance and fostering a supportive learning environment, the intervention of the DsLAC initiative has the potential to empower teachers to overcome their initial hesitations and excel in teaching Practical Research effectively. Similarly, collaborative learning action cell mentoring program can increase the level of self-efficacy of the out-of-field SHS teachers (Sumbilla et al., 2022).

The involvement of the District Learning Action Cell signifies a proactive approach to addressing the professional development needs of educators, particularly in areas where they may feel less confident or experienced. Through tailored support, collaborative learning opportunities, and access to resources, teachers can enhance their expertise in Practical Research and create enriching learning experiences for their students. By leveraging the resources and guidance provided by the DsLAC initiative, educators can navigate the challenges of teaching Practical Research with confidence and competence, ultimately elevating the quality of education within their institutions.

Table 2
Teachers' Experiences and Learnings After the District Learning Action Cell

After the Intervention (District Learning Action Cell)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teachers possessed the profound expertise in instructing practical research. • Teachers possessed the capability to expertly craft research proposals. • Teachers exhibited confidence in their ability to effectively impart knowledge and facilitate understanding in Practical Research subject. • Teachers acquired valuable insights into practical research through the intervention.
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The District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC) represents an innovative program aimed at facilitating collaborative learning sessions among teachers to address the challenges encountered in teaching practical

research. These sessions serve as valuable platforms for educators to engage in open discussions, exchange creative ideas, and seek guidance on effectively delivering practical research lessons. Through the intervention of DsLAC, teachers have acquired essential knowledge and gained profound insights necessary for teaching practical research effectively. This newfound expertise has empowered them to skillfully develop research proposals and navigate the complexities of the subject with confidence.

The impact of the DsLAC intervention is evident in the increased confidence displayed by teachers in their ability to impart knowledge and foster understanding in Practical Research. Their enhanced proficiency in this area not only elevates their individual capabilities but also contributes to a positive transformation in the educational experience of both students and fellow educators. By honing their expertise through DsLAC, teachers are better equipped to engage students, deliver comprehensive lessons, and create a dynamic learning environment that promotes critical thinking and research skills.

Furthermore, the collaborative nature of the DsLAC sessions fosters a culture of continuous improvement and professional development among educators. Through the exchange of ideas and experiences, teachers benefit from peer mentorship and support, allowing for the enhancement of teaching practices and the implementation of innovative instructional strategies. The sense of camaraderie and shared learning within the DsLAC framework not only enhances individual teacher growth but also cultivates a community of practice that values collaboration, reflection, and ongoing learning.

In essence, the District Learning Action Cell initiative has proven to be instrumental in empowering teachers with the knowledge, skills, and confidence needed to excel in teaching Practical Research. By fostering a supportive environment for professional growth and collaboration, DsLAC has not only elevated the expertise of educators but has also enriched the educational landscape, ultimately benefiting students and educators alike.

CONCLUSION

Prior to the intervention of the District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC), educators exhibited notable dearth in both confidence and proficiency when tasked with instructing Practical Research. They expressed a lack of comprehensive understanding in this subject and foster doubts regarding the complexities of the subject. At first, they expressed hesitation to take on the task of teaching Practical Research. Teachers also expressed apprehensions about the difficulties involved in conveying Practical Research concepts.

However, after the District Learning Action Cell intervention spearheaded by the researchers, a discernible transformation has taken place amongst educators. They have acquired a heightened level of expertise, confidence, and a significantly enhanced comprehension of the discipline of Practical Research. These educators now possess a range of essential skills and capabilities necessary for effectively teaching Practical Research subject. Through comprehensive training initiatives led by the researchers, teachers have undergone significant development, refined their teaching skills and enhanced their grasp of the subject matter.

The intervention of the District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC) has been remarkably successful and effective in enhancing teachers' capacity to effectively teach Practical Research. The evident improvements in teachers' confidence, knowledge, and proficiency underscore the positive impact of intervention's group learning approach, providing a supportive platform for collaboration and skill development. Through this collaborative environment, District Learning Action Cell has not only enabled teachers to surpass the initial challenges but also empowered them to excel in delivering Practical Research education. The outcomes clearly illustrate the transformative potential of targeted interventions in bolstering teacher readiness and capabilities within specific subject areas, emphasizing the significance of structured support and collaborative learning environments in the professional development of teachers.

ACTION PLAN

Dissemination and Utilization Report

To effectively address teachers' apprehension in teaching Practical Research, the implementation of the District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC) intervention is proposed for San Fernando District II. This initiative aims to provide educators with the necessary support and guidance to enhance their teaching practices in research subjects.

To encourage teachers to embrace the DsLAC intervention, a comprehensive strategy is recommended. Firstly, organizing training workshops focusing on practical research teaching methods, interactive activities, and

sharing of successful strategies is crucial. These workshops should incorporate hands-on activities, allowing teachers to experience and apply the strategies in a practical setting.

Secondly, establishing a peer mentorship program where experienced teachers can support their colleagues will create a nurturing and collaborative learning environment. This program can facilitate knowledge sharing, provide practical advice, and offer emotional support to teachers who are new to teaching Practical Research.

Thirdly, promoting collaborative learning groups and opportunities for professional growth will foster continuous learning and skill enhancement among teachers. These groups can provide a platform for teachers to share best practices, discuss challenges, and learn from each other's experiences.

To ensure widespread awareness and understanding of the DsLAC intervention, a multi-pronged approach will be employed. School leaders and district supervisors will be informed about the intervention through informational meetings or briefings emphasizing its goals and advantages. These sessions will be integrated into in-service training seminars for teachers to ensure their active participation and engagement.

By implementing these strategies, the educators in San Fernando District II can receive the necessary support and guidance to enhance their teaching practices in Practical Research, leading to improved student learning outcomes and a more robust research culture within the district.

PLANS FOR UTILIZATION AND DISSEMINATION

To address teachers' concerns about teaching Practical Research, the implementation of the District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC) intervention is recommended for San Fernando District II. This initiative aims to support educators in effectively teaching research subjects.

A comprehensive strategy is proposed to encourage teachers to embrace the DsLAC intervention. Firstly, organizing training workshops focusing on practical research teaching methods, interactive activities, and sharing of successful strategies is crucial. Establishing a peer mentorship program where seasoned teachers can support their colleagues will create a nurturing atmosphere. Moreover, promoting collaborative learning groups and opportunities for professional growth will foster continuous learning and skill enhancement among teachers.

Various approaches will be employed to promote and endorse the DsLAC intervention, including mentorship and coaching. School leaders and district supervisors will be informed about the intervention through informational meetings or briefings emphasizing its goals and advantages. These sessions will be integrated into in-service training seminars for teachers to ensure widespread awareness and understanding of the initiative. By implementing these strategies, the educators in San Fernando District II can receive the necessary support and guidance to enhance their teaching practices in Practical Research.

WORK PLANS AND TIMELINES FOR RESEARCH IMPLEMENTATION

1st Proponent : **Cerele B. Abasolo**

Title of Action Research:

District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC): Intervention to Teachers' Apprehension to Teach Practical Research

TASKS / ACTIVITIES	TARGET DATE	PERSON(S) RESPONSIBLE / INVOLVED
Pre-Implementation Phase		
1. Researchers ask consent from the district supervisor and the principal of Sangat National High School, which is the researcher's affiliated institution and informed consent and address other ethical concerns.	January 28,2024	Researchers, Principal & School Heads , Public district supervisor
2. The researchers orients the senior high school teachers in San Fernando II, particularly those handling research subjects.	February 8,,2024	Researchers, School Heads, School Research coordinator, Teacher
3. Researchers conducted a focus group discussion with the senior high school teachers in San Fernando II District to identify their concerns about teaching the Practical Research subject.	February 23,,2024	Researchers, Research coordinator, Teachers

Implementation Phase		
1. Researchers takes the lead and puts the District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC) into action.	February 27, March 1, 8, 15, 22, 29, - April 5, 12, 19, 26, 2024	Researchers, School Heads, School Research coordinator, Teachers
2. Teachers take an active part in cooperative learning exercises. They get advice on how to effectively teach the Practical Research course, share ideas, and discuss the difficulties they have encountered.	February 27, March 1, 8, 15, 22, 29, - April 5, 12, 19, 26, 2024	Researchers, Research coordinator, Teachers
3. The researchers informs the research participants about the goals, parameters, and timeline of the study. Secures their voluntary and informed consent and addresses other ethical concerns.	February 27, March 1, 8, 15, 22, 29, - April 5, 12, 19, 26, 2024	Researchers, Research coordinator, Teachers
Post Implementation Phase		
1. The Researchers consolidate the results; tally and compute the data using the appropriate statistical tools.	February 27, March 1, 8, 15, 22, 29, - April 5, 12, 19, 26, 2024	Researchers

APPENDICES

RESEARCH MANAGEMENT: APPLICATION FORM AND ENDORSEMENT OF IMMEDIATE SUPERVISOR(S) OF THE PROPONENT(S) TEMPLATE

A. RESEARCH INFORMATION

TITLE OF ACTION RESEARCH

District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC): Intervention to Teachers Apprehension to Teach Practical Research

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE RESEARCH

In San Fernando District II, the noble aim of education encounters a significant challenge as teachers lack confidence and feel hesitant about teaching practical research subjects. To tackle this issue, the researcher implements the District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC) intervention. This initiative entails collaborative learning sessions where teachers can openly discuss their difficulties, exchange insights, and receive guidance on teaching practical research. By fostering a supportive and collaborative atmosphere, the intervention aims to bolster teachers' confidence and capabilities in delivering practical research course.

RESEARCH AGENDA CATEGORY	
<p>(Please check <u>only one</u>) Main Themes</p> <p>1. Teaching and Learning ☐ a. Instruction ☐ b. Curriculum ☐ c. Learners ☐ d. Assessment ☒ e. Learning Outcomes</p> <p>2. Child Protection ☐ a. Bullying ☐ b. Teenage Pregnancy ☐ c. Child Abuse ☐ d. Addiction ☐ e. Media Consumption</p> <p>3. Human Resource Development ☐ a. Teaching and Non-Teaching Qualifications and Hiring ☐ b. Career Development ☐ c. Employee Welfare</p> <p>4. Governance ☐ a. Planning ☐ b. Finance ☐ c. Program Management ☐ d. Transparency and Accountability ☐ e. Evaluation</p>	<p>(Please check any, if applicable) Cut-Across Themes</p> <p>1. Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) ☐ a. Prevention and Mitigation ☐ b. Preparedness ☐ c. Response ☐ d. Rehabilitation and Recovery</p> <p>2. Gender and Development (GAD) ☐ 3. Inclusive Education ☐ 4. Others (please specify): _____</p> <hr/> <p style="text-align: center;">RESEARCH SCOPE <i>(please check <u>only one</u>)</i></p> <p>☐ National ☐ Region ☒ Division ☐ District ☐ School</p> <hr/> <p style="text-align: center;">RESEARCH CATEGORY <i>(please check <u>only one</u>)</i></p> <p>☐ Action Research ☐ Basic Research</p>
FUND SOURCE (e.g. BERF, SEF, others)*	AMOUNT
TOTAL AMOUNT	

RESEARCH MANAGEMENT: APPLICATION FORM AND ENDORSEMENT OF IMMEDIATE SUPERVISOR(S) OF THE PROPONENT(S) TEMPLATE

B. RESEARCH INFORMATION

<p>TITLE OF ACTION RESEARCH District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC): Intervention to Teachers Apprehension to Teach Practical Research</p>
<p>SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE RESEARCH In San Fernando District II, the noble aim of education encounters a significant challenge as teachers lack confidence and feel hesitant about teaching practical research subjects. To tackle this issue, the researcher implements the District Learning Action Cell (DsLAC) intervention. This initiative entails collaborative learning sessions where teachers can openly discuss their difficulties, exchange insights, and receive guidance on teaching practical research. By fostering a supportive and collaborative atmosphere, the intervention aims to bolster teachers' confidence and capabilities in delivering practical research course.</p>

PROPONENT INFORMATION

LEAD PROPONENT / INDIVIDUAL PROPONENT

/

LAST NAME: Abasolo		FIRST NAME: Cerelo		MIDDLE NAME: Barolo	
BIRTHDATE (MM/DD/YYYY) 02/09/1979		SEX: ☒ Male ☐ Female		POSITION TIC	
				DESIGNATION: (if applicable) District research coordinator	
CONTACT NUMBER 1: 0997710036		CONTACT NUMBER 2:		EMAIL ADDRESS: cerelo.abasolo@deped.gov.	
NAME OF SCHOOL / DISTRICT / OFFICE ASSIGNED Sangat National High School				CONTACT NUMBER OF SCHOOL / DISTRICT / OFFICE	
ADDRESS OF SCHOOL / DISTRICT / OFFICE ASSIGNED Sangat, San Fernando ,Cebu				DIVISION Cebu	REGION VII
EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT (DEGREE TITLE) <i>enumerate from bachelor's degree up to doctorate degree</i>		TITLE OF THESIS / RELATED RESEARCH PROJECT Enhancing Learners' Physics Performance through Science Club Integration			

EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT (DEGREE TITLE) <i>enumerate from bachelor's degree up to doctorate degree</i>		TITLE OF THESIS / RELATED RESEARCH PROJECT			
SIGNATURE OF PROPONENT:					

RESEARCH MANAGEMENT:

DECLARATION OF ABSENCE OF CONFLICT OF INTEREST

1. We, Cerelo B. Abasolo, understand that conflict of interest refers to situations in which financial or other personal considerations may compromise my/our judgement in evaluating, conducting, or reporting research.
2. We hereby declare that I/We do not have any personal conflict of interest that may arise from my/our application and submission of my/our research proposal. I/We understand that my/our research proposal

may be returned to me/us if found out that there is conflict of interest during the initial screening as per item A(ii), Section V(B) of the Research Management Guidelines.

3. Further, in case of any form of conflict of interest (possible or actual) which may inadvertently emerge during the conduct of my/our research. I/We will duly report it to the research committee for immediate action.
4. We understand that I/We may be held accountable by the Department of Education and (insert grant mechanism) for any conflict of interest which I/We have intentionally concealed.

	Lead Proponent	Second Proponent	Third Proponent
Full Name	Cereilo B. Abasolo		
Position / Designation	Teacher 3		
Division / District/ School/ Unit/ Office	Sangat National High School-San Fernando II District		
Signature			
Date	February 22, 2024		

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